

Synthetic, spectral, thermal and antibacterial studies on copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes using NNO donor Schiff bases

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Copper(II) and zinc (II) complexes of Schiff bases, derived from substituted 2-aminothiazoles and *o*-hydroxyaldehydes, have been synthesized. The complexes are monomeric, possessing 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry and are non-electrolytic in nature. The Zn^{II} complexes have been characterized by thermal analyses and X-ray diffractometry. The kinetic parameters (*n*, *E*, *Z*, ΔS and *G*) estimated using Coats-Redfern, MacCallum-Tanner and Horowitz-Metzger methods are in good mutual agreement. The powder X-ray diffraction studies suggest a tetragonal crystal system for the Zn^{II} complexes. Antibacterial activities of the complexes have also been studied.

Schiff bases possess strong ability to form metal complexes¹, and they deserve a proper attention because of their biological properties². The Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of Schiff bases are also biologically active³ and they exhibit enhanced activities as compared to their parent ligands. Thiazole derivatives possess a wide spectrum of biological activities⁴ and therefore Schiff bases containing thiazole moiety, and their metal complexes are expected to be bioactive compounds.

In this communication, we report syntheses and characterisations of new Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of Schiff bases (1-9) (Fig. 1) derived from 4-(*p*-*R*-phenyl)-2-aminothiazole and *o*-hydroxyaldehydes. These Schiff bases

behave as NNO-tridentate ligands, HL (H refers to the phenolato hydrogen).

Results and discussion

The copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes are crystalline solids, prepared by refluxing the metal acetate and the ligand (1 : 2 ratio) in ethanol. The olive green Cu^{II} complexes and orange red Zn^{II} complexes are soluble in chloroform, benzene and nitrobenzene and melt with decomposition above 250°. The elemental analyses data (Tables 1 and 2) suggest 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry of the complexes. Very low molar conductance values ($< 10 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) in nitrobenzene indicate that the complexes are non-electrolytic and monomeric in nature (ML₂ type complexes).

The Cu^{II}L₂ complexes exhibit bands in the electronic spectra at ~15000 and ~26000 cm⁻¹. The first band is broad and asymmetric and is assigned to ²T_{2g} ← ²E_g transition in an octahedral geometry. The second band is sharp and intense ($\epsilon \sim 1000 \text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$), and may be due to ligand to metal (M ← L) charge transfer. The magnetic moment values of the complexes lie in the range 1.88–2.00 B.M. The electronic spectral data⁵ coupled with magnetic moment values⁶ suggest a distorted octahedral geometry for the complexes. The Zn^{II} complexes are diamagnetic and display a sharp and intense band at ~26000 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon \sim 1000 \text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) probably due to ligand to metal charge transfer. Thus, an octahedral geometry is proposed for these complexes.

Infrared spectra :

IR spectra of the ligands (1-9) exhibit bands at ~2900

HL	R	R'
1	Br	H
2	Br	5-CH ₃
3	Br	4-CH ₃
4	Br	3-CH ₃
5	Br	5-Br
6	Br	5-Cl
7	Br	
8	H	
9	H	5-CH ₃

Fig. 1

Table 1. Elemental and electronic spectral data of copper(II) complexes*

Sl. no.	Compd.	R	R'	Metal% Found (Calcd.)	λ_{\max} cm ⁻¹	10Dq cm ⁻¹
1.	Cu(C ₁₆ H ₁₀ BrN ₂ OS) ₂	Br	H	8.01 (8.15)	5100	15100
2.	Cu(C ₁₇ H ₁₂ BrN ₂ OS) ₂	Br	5-CH ₃	7.80 (7.86)	15200	15200
3.	Cu(C ₁₇ H ₁₂ BrN ₂ OS) ₂	Br	4-CH ₃	7.81 (7.86)	15100	15100
4.	Cu(C ₁₇ H ₁₂ BrN ₂ OS) ₂	Br	3-CH ₃	7.80 (7.86)	15200	15200
5.	Cu(C ₁₆ H ₉ Br ₂ N ₂ OS) ₂	Br	5-Br	6.85 (6.77)	15400	15400
6.	Cu(C ₁₆ H ₉ BrClN ₂ OS) ₂	Br	5-Cl	7.53 (7.48)	15400	15400
7.	Cu(C ₂₀ H ₁₂ BrN ₂ OS) ₂	Br		7.30 (7.22)	15500	15500

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

(a broad and weak band due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding between hydroxyl hydrogen and nitrogen of the azomethine group), ~1630 (C=N) and ~1280 cm⁻¹ (C-O) which are in agreement with the earlier report⁷. The absence of ν_{OH} mode in the complexes indicate the utilization of phenolic-OH in metal-oxygen bond formation. ν_{C-O} and $\nu_{C=N}$ modes occur at ~1330 and ~1580 cm⁻¹, respectively in the complexes. The shifting of ν_{C-O} towards higher frequency as compared to the ligands is due to the conversion of hydrogen bonded structure into a covalent metal bonded structure⁷. Lowering of $\nu_{C=N}$ in the complexes as compared to the ligands, is due to reduction of double bond character of carbon-nitrogen bond of the azomethine group⁷. Thus it is suggested that the coordination of ligand-to-metal in the complexes takes place through oxygen of the phenolic OH and nitrogen of the azomethine group.

Antibacterial activity :

The ligands (1–9) and their Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes were tested for their antibacterial activity against *Salmonella typhi* by serial dilution technique⁸ in DMF in the concentration range 5–50 μ g/ml. The MIC values for the ligands

lie in the range 20–26 μ g/ml. The values of the Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes lie in the range 10–15 and 12–16 μ g/ml, respectively.

It is observed that the Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes show enhanced antibacterial activity as compared to the ligands. This is because of the chelation, which reduces the polarity of metal ion due to partial sharing of its positive charge with donor groups and also due to the delocalization of π electrons over whole chelate ring. Thus chelation increases lipophilic character in the complexes and results in enhancement of activity⁹.

Thermal analysis :

The Zn^{II} complexes are characterised by thermal analyses. Zn(C₂₀H₁₃N₂OS)₂, R = H and R' = , is chosen for study. In the TG curve, there is no weight loss upto 250° and this rules out the presence of any water molecule in the complex. It undergoes decomposition in two stages : Stage I (290–445°), 41.79% weight loss, and stage II (537–670°), 35.78% weight loss. The residue 10.87% weight (theoretical value 11.3% weight) remaining at the end of second stage corresponds to ZnO. Thus the complex is thermally stable.

In order to calculate the kinetic parameters viz. *n* (order of reaction), *E* (energy of activation), *Z* (pre-exponential factor), ΔS (entropy of activation) and *G* (free energy change), three methods have been used namely Coats-Redfern (C.R.), MacCallum-Tanner (M.T.) and Horowitz-Metzger (H.M.).

Coats-Redfern method¹⁰ :

$$\log \left(\frac{1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1-n}}{(1 - n)T^2} \right) = \log \frac{ZR}{Eg} \left(1 - \frac{2RT}{E} \right) - \frac{E}{2.303R} \cdot \frac{1}{T} \quad (1)$$

Table 2. Elemental analyses data of zinc(II) complexes*

Sl. no.	Compd.	R	R'	M% Found (calcd.)
1.	Zn(C ₁₆ H ₁₀ BrN ₂ OS) ₂	Br	H	8.50 (8.37)
2.	Zn(C ₁₇ H ₁₂ BrN ₂ OS) ₂	Br	5-CH ₃	8.15 (8.08)
3.	Zn(C ₁₇ H ₁₂ BrN ₂ OS) ₂	Br	4-CH ₃	8.15 (8.08)
4.	Zn(C ₁₇ H ₁₂ BrN ₂ OS) ₂	Br	3-CH ₃	8.01 (8.08)
5.	Zn(C ₁₆ H ₉ Br ₂ N ₂ OS) ₂	Br	5-Br	6.88 (6.96)
6.	Zn(C ₁₆ H ₉ BrClN ₂ OS) ₂	Br	5-Cl	7.75 (7.69)
7.	Zn(C ₂₀ H ₁₂ BrN ₂ OS) ₂	Br		7.40 (7.42)
8.	Zn(C ₂₀ H ₁₃ N ₂ OS) ₂	H		8.89 (9.03)
9.	Zn(C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ OS) ₂	H	5-CH ₃	10.15 (10.03)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

MacCallum-Tanner method¹¹ :

$$\log \left(\frac{1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1-n}}{(1-n)} \right) = \log \frac{ZE}{Rq} - 0.485E^{0.435} - \frac{0.449 + 0.217E}{T} \cdot 10^3 \quad (2)$$

Horowitz-Metzger method¹² :

$$\log \left(\frac{1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1-n}}{(1-n)} \right) = \log \frac{ZRT_s^2}{Eq} - \frac{E}{2.303RT_s} + \frac{E\theta}{2.303RT_s^2} \quad (3)$$

where α is the fraction decomposed, q the heating rate, T the absolute temperature, T_s the temperature at half weight loss and $\theta = (T - T_s)$. The left-hand-side of eqns. (1) and (2) was plotted against $1/T$ and against $\theta/(T - T_s)$ for eqn. (3). By using different values of order of reaction, straight-line was fitted by regression. The highest value of r , the correlation coefficient, gave the correct value of n . From the slope and the intercept, E and Z values were calculated. Using E and Z values, the values of ΔS and G were determined.

The values of n , E , Z , ΔS and G estimated by all three methods are in good mutual agreement (Table 3). The value of E is sufficiently high and is comparable with other observations¹³.

Table 3. Calculation of kinetic parameters by Coats-Redfern (C.R.), MacCallum-Tanner (M.T.) and Horowitz-Metzger (H.M.) methods

Compound : $Zn(C_{20}H_{13}N_2OS)_2$, (R = H, R' =)				
Step	Kinetic parameter	C.R.	M.T.	H.M.
I	E	34.72	35.46	40.27
	n	1.39	1.39	1.65
	Z	$06.49E + 09$	$01.14E + 10$	$09.87E + 11$
	ΔS	-7.62	-7.05	-2.6
	G	39.59	39.97	41.93
	E	63.93	65.80	70.56
II	n	1.146	1.146	1.25
	Z	$01.15E + 14$	$05.69E + 14$	$08.59E + 15$
	ΔS	1.851	3.45	6.16
	G	62.325	62.80	65.20

Units : E (kcal mol⁻¹), Z (s⁻¹), ΔS (JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹), G (kcal mol⁻¹).

X-ray diffraction studies :

The Zn^{II} complexes are also characterised by powder XRD studies with a view to find the type of crystal system.

$Zn(C_{17}H_{13}N_2OS)_2$, R = H, R' = 5-CH₃, is chosen for study. The XRD data is given in Table 4. There are 34 reflections (2θ) between 11.14 and 68.63° with maximum at $2\theta = 23.03^\circ$ and $d = 3.8586 \text{ \AA}$. The general procedure and methods of calculations are based on the published work¹⁴. The observed and calculated values of d and θ are quite consistent (Table 4). In order to evaluate lattice parameters (a , b and c) of the unit cell and cell volume, we first assumed a tetragonal crystal system for the complex. The cell parameters calculated for the complex are given in Table 4 ($a = b = 14.5867 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 35.3568 \text{ \AA}$; $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$) and which are found to be in accordance with those required for a tetragonal crystal system¹⁵ where $a = b \neq c$ and $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$. Thus it may be concluded that the crystal system of the complex is tetragonal.

Conclusion : In the light of above discussion we have proposed a distorted octahedral geometry for the Cu^{II} complexes and an octahedral geometry for the Zn^{II} complexes. The ligands behave as NNO tridentate, coordinating through nitrogen of the azomethine⁷, nitrogen of the thiazole moiety¹⁶ and oxygen of the phenolic OH group⁷ (NNO donor set) (Fig. 2). The complexes are biologically active and exhibit enhanced antibacterial activities compared to their parent ligands. The thermal studies of a Zn^{II} complex indicate that the complex is thermally stable. The XRD studies of a Zn^{II} complex suggest a tetragonal crystal system.

Experimental

The elemental analyses (C, H and N) were performed by using microanalytical techniques. The molecular weights were determined by cryoscopic method and the metal contents were estimated gravimetrically. The electrical conductivities of the complexes in nitrobenzene were measured by a Philips conductivity bridge with dip type cell and room temperature magnetic moments by Gouy method. The diamagnetic corrections were made applying Pascals constants¹⁷. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu A/160 spectrophotometer, and IR spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer spectrometer. The thermal measurements (Perkin-Elmer TGS-2 thermal analyzer) were carried out at Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, Nagpur University, Nagpur; heating rate was 20°/min in air atmosphere. X-Ray diffractogram was run in the range 10–80° using a Philips PW-1710 diffractometer attached to a digitized computer along with graphical assembly where CuK α radiation source connected with a tube of Cu-NF 2 kV/20 mA was used.

4-(*p*-R-Phenyl)-2-aminothiazole, R = H and Br, were prepared by the reported method¹⁸. The mass spectral data of 4-(*p*-bromophenyl)-2-aminothiazole (m.p. 176°) is given, m/z (relative intensity %) : M⁺ 254/256* (100), 212/214* (28/30), 133 (25), 89 (28) (peaks marked with (*) corre-

Table 4. X-ray data of $Zn(C_{17}H_{13}N_2OS)_2 \cdot [R = H, R' = 5-CH_3]$

Peak no.	2θ	d_{obs}	d_{cal}	Q_{obs}	Q_{cal}	$dQ \cdot 10^4$	I/I_{max} (%)	hkl
01	11.140	7.936	—	0.0159	—	1	18	—
02	11.285	7.8343	7.765	0.0163	0.0166	1	16.56	113
03	12.130	7.2904	7.293	0.0188	0.0188	2	7.44	20
04	13.015	6.7966	6.742	0.0216	0.0220	2	5.88	22
05	13.975	6.3318	6.363	0.0249	0.0247	2	1.58	15
06	15.280	5.7938	5.832	0.0298	0.0294	2	1.80	115
07	16.735	5.2932	5.249	0.0357	0.0363	2	13.54	124
08	17.290	5.1245	5.116	0.0381	0.0382	2	4.87	116
09	18.105	4.8957	4.862	0.0417	0.0423	2	6.75	30
10	19.895	4.4590	4.454	0.0503	0.0504	3	9.71	224
11	21.105	4.2060	4.230	0.0565	0.0559	3	7.44	18
12	22.875	3.8844	3.881	0.0663	0.0664	3	74.21	226
13	23.030	3.8586	3.863	0.0672	0.0670	3	100	135
14	23.585	3.7691	3.780	0.0704	0.0700	3	22.68	28
15	24.670	3.6057	3.608	0.0769	0.0768	3	10.82	227
16	25.410	3.5024	3.503	0.0815	0.0815	3	6.30	37
17	26.665	3.3403	3.345	0.0896	0.0894	3	07.92	1110
18	28.260	3.1553	3.158	0.1004	0.1003	4	26.54	237
19	28.990	3.0775	3.092	0.1056	0.1046	4	15.18	335
20	29.865	2.9893	2.991	0.1119	0.1118	4	04.50	139
21	33.145	2.7006	2.697	0.1371	0.1375	4	21.46	55
22	33.885	2.6433	2.640	0.1431	0.1435	4	8.92	253
23	34.775	2.5776	2.579	0.1505	0.1504	4	16.56	440
24	35.670	2.5150	2.519	0.1581	0.1576	4	12.30	443
25	36.790	2.4409	2.447	0.1665	0.1670	4	10.82	353
26	37.440	2.4000	2.401	0.1736	0.1734	4	4.87	158
27	38.970	2.3093	2.309	0.1875	0.1875	5	4.14	258
28	39.895	2.2578	2.259	0.1962	0.1959	5	7.92	452
29	45.075	2.0097	2.010	0.2476	0.2476	5	13.54	462
30	47.565	1.9101	1.910	0.2741	0.2742	5	7.44	177
31	55.425	1.6564	1.654	0.3645	0.3656	6	6.75	89
32	57.545	1.6003	1.602	0.3905	0.3896	6	4.50	668
33	60.500	1.5290	1.529	0.4277	0.4278	6	4.87	5710
34	68.530	1.3664	1.366	0.5356	0.5359	7	5.46	4910

Refined calculated cell parameters for a tetragonal crystal system.

$a = b = 14.5867$, $c = 35.3568$ Å.

Volume of unit cell = 7522.9 Å³.

Particle size = 246.35 Å.

spond to isotopic bromine).

The Schiff bases (**1–9**) were prepared by condensation of equimolar amounts of substituted 2-aminothiazole and *o*-hydroxyaldehyde, in ethanol. The crystals separated on cooling the solution were recrystallized from ethanol and

dried under reduced pressure, yield ~70–75%. The ligands gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses. M.ps. are given in parantheses : **1** (172°), **2** (187°), **3** (182°), **4** (180°), **5** (178°), **6** (181°), **7** (170°), **8** (157°) and **9** (152°). All melting points are uncorrected.

Fig. 2

Copper (II) complexes : A solution of 0.01 mole of copper acetate in ethanol was added to the ethanolic solution of 0.02 mole of *o*-hydroxyaldehyde and 0.02 mole of substituted 2-aminothiazole or 0.02 mole of Schiff base. The mixture was refluxed on water bath for five minutes and then the temperature of the water bath was maintained at 45–50° for 0.5 h. The olive green crystals separated, were filtered, washed with hot ethanol and dried in vacu (yield ~ 60%).

Zinc(II) complexes : 0.01 mol of zinc acetate in ethanol was added to the ethanolic solution of 0.02 mole *o*-hydroxyaldehyde and 0.02 mole of substituted 2-aminothiazole or 0.02 mole of Schiff base. The mixture was heated on a water bath until the orange coloured crystals separated out. It was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in vacu (yield ~60%).

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